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LEXICOGRAMMATICAL CHOICES IN THE CHILD RIGHTS ACT NIGERIA

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Abstract

Studies on The Child's Rights Act in Nigeria (henceforth, (CRANig.) have approached the study mostly from the legal perspective, and the challenges with the domestication of the law in Nigeria. Linguistic studies on the Act are still unfolding. This paper fills this gap by investigating the lexicogrammatical features embedded in the Child's Rights Act (Nigeria). It specifically examines the Transitivity systems and the selection of connectors and legal jargons encoded and their portrayal of meanings in the Act. The Hallidayan functional approach to grammatical meanings is the theoretical approach to the study. Findings from the analysis reveal that The Act contains carefully selected lexicogrammatical resources, which are structured to depict the epistemic understanding of the world of the Nigerian legal system about children and their rights. This includes knowledge, expectations, justification, events, states, and consciousness related to the treatment of children by all those who are stakeholders in their well-being.

Keywords: lexicogrammar, transitivity, Child's Rights Act, experiential meanings

1. Introduction

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the child is an important international treaty adopted in 1989 by the General Assembly of the United Nations. The treaty recognises children as human beings with some distinct set of rights. This law was domesticated in Nigeria in 2003. The law spells out the rights of a child detailing rules that draw attention to the rights of special protection and care afforded to children. This includes their protection against any form of assault, discrimination and violence. The law emphasises that children are individuals who are entitled to some basic rights, such as the need for shelter and security (Detrick, Doek & Cantwell, 1992). According to Akhuzada *et al* (2015), Convention on the Right of Children has four guiding principles, which are equality, best interest of the child, life, survival and development and participation.

However, in contemporary times, millions of Nigerian children suffer some forms of physical, emotional or sexual violence. According to a 2014 survey conducted by the Nigerian Population Commission with support from UNICEF and the United States Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, six out of ten Nigerian children experience at least one of these forms of violence before they reach eighteen years (<https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/reports/ending-violence-against-children-nigeria>).

The present study is an investigation of the lexicogrammatical features in the Child's Rights Acts Nigeria (CRANig). Children all over the world are yet to be accorded the relevant and necessary attention they deserve to prepare them for the very important task of assuming future leadership positions in the society. Millions of them across the world suffer different kinds of physical, emotional and sexual violence, which include maltreatment, neglect, bullying, trafficking and so forth (UNICEF 2020). This disturbing development prompted the United Nations General

Assembly, on 20th November, 1989, to adopt the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). A year later, the Organisation for African Unity (OAU) Assembly of Heads of States and Government adopted the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child on July 11, 1990. It was thirteen years after that The Child's Rights Bill was passed into law by the Nigeria's National Assembly on July 31, 2003. This legal document which protects the rights of Nigeria children has been adopted by all the **thirty-six** (36) states and the Federal Capital Territory in Nigeria. Despite the adoption of the Act, there still exists serious cases of child's rights abuse in the country and these include child trafficking, hawking, child labour, child marriage, child slavery and so on (Adamu 2025, Fwafu et al 2025, Onyejelem *et al.* 2025).

Since it is important that the rights of a child be protected by the law of every country, understanding the contents of the document that spells out these rights is necessary in order to identify the precise roles of participants, processes and circumstances guiding the operation of the document. This understanding would assist in uncovering the embedded meanings in the document.

This important document derives from the cognitive construct that children are important members of any society, who should be well taken care of. A study of the CRA(Nig) from the linguistic perspective can help to draw attention to the lexicogrammatical structures employed in constructing the document. Such study **would** also reveal the representation of the content of the experiences in the document. This study therefore focuses on analysing the lexicogrammatical contents in CRANig with the view to understanding how such lexicogrammatical features are deployed for meaning making within the legal context of the nation.

Research Aim and Objectives

The research set out to investigate the lexicogrammatical contents of selected sections of the Child Rights Act (Nigeria). The objectives are to:

- (i) identify the experiential meanings in the selected sections;
- (ii) analyse the clauses in the sections with a view to show the participants, processes and circumstantial elements in them; and
- (iii) discuss the implications of the lexicogrammatical resources for the dissemination of legal discourse in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Despite the fact that children all over the world are regarded as leaders of tomorrow, they are not accorded the necessary attention to prepare them for this huge task ahead. Millions of them all over the world are victims of rape, slavery and other abuses. The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) outlines the human rights to be respected and protected for every child under eighteen (18) years and requires that these rights be implemented. As a result, a draft of the Child's Rights Bill aimed at principally enacting into law in Nigeria the principles enshrined in the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the AU Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child was passed into law by Nigeria's National Assembly on July 31, 2003. It was assented by the President then, Olusegun Obasanjo in 2003 and promulgated as the Child's Right Act 2003. The Act is a legal document that sets out the rights and responsibilities of a child in Nigeria and which consolidates all laws relating to children into one single legislation, as well as specifying the duties and obligations of governments, parents and other authorities, organisations and bodies.

Since the Federal Government and the States have passed the bill, it is normal that the child's rights should be protected and any breach of such act would attract a punishment to the

offender. However, besides passing the law at the States' level, its strict enforcement is yet to be fully implemented. It is rather unfortunate that in States where this Bill has been adopted, there are repeated cases of child abuse. In many parts of Nigeria, children are married off as part of a culture, thereby denying their right to education. Many children are sold into slavery and engaged to provide income for their parents. Cases of young girls being raped one time or the other are rampant in some parts of the country. It is therefore necessary to carry out a linguistic study of the Child Rights Acts in order to provide objective linguistic evidence of how textual units are used to project meanings in legal texts. This inquiry will make the interpretation of the law easier due to the breakdown of its functions and social relevance in the analysis that would be provided.

The goal of the CRA(Nig) is to remedy some of the past injustices against children in need of care and protection (Abdulraheem, 2016: 435). Bamgbose (1998:7) holds the view that the child justice administration regime is based on the philosophy of reformation and rehabilitation of child offenders and children in need of care and protection as these children are immature and should not be treated as adult offenders.

For Iguh and Nosike (2011:2) though a landmark legislative achievement, the CRA 2003 has not translated into an improved child's right protection throughout the Federation owing to the fact that having been enacted at the national level, the States are expected to formally adopt the Act for domestication as State laws. The reason is that issues of child protection are on the residual list of the Nigerian Constitution, giving States exclusive responsibility and jurisdiction to make laws relevant to their specific situations. Section 1 of the Act provides the best interest of a child to be the primary consideration in all actions concerning a child, whether undertaken by an individual, public or private body, institution, court of law or administrative or legislative authority. Under the Act (Section 13), every child has the right to survival and development, identity, freedom

of association and peaceful assemble and no child shall be subjected to any form of discrimination and must have his or her dignity respected at all times. Sections 21 to -24 criminalises child marriage and betrothal, tattoos and skin marks. Sections 25 to – 33 kicks against the exposure of children to the use, production or trafficking of narcotic drugs or other criminal activities, abduction of a child for exploitative labour, alms begging, street or roadside hawking, unlawful sexual intercourse and other forms of sexual exploitations.

In addition to the list of rights of the child, sections 50 to - 67 of the CRA 2003 sets out the responsibilities of government and parents to provide structures and facilities, homes and a conducive environment for the full development of children. It empowers the court to make protection and supervision orders in respect of children in need of care and protection.

According to United Nations Child’s Emergency Funds (UNICEF); despite the rhetoric in the international and national community about the importance of children’s rights, the rights, norms and principles involved are regularly ignored and seriously violated throughout the world on a scale unmatched in the field of Human Right implementation. The non-implementations, and of course, the vulnerability of the child makes the child to be susceptible to many challenges among which are child abuse, child labour, which entail a child growing up under conditions harmful to their health usually for long hours for very low wages; child neglect which is seen as a deficit in meeting a child’s basic needs, child prostitution and lack of education.

Children's Rights is a topic of interest to scholars in many disciplines. Existing studies on the CRA(Nig) have investigated and determined the legal functions of its use (Akinwumi 2010, Tajudeen 2015, Giwa 2023, Erhurhu & Ahwefeaada 2025), its media coverage, (Awosola & Omoera 2008, Uzochukwu et al 2015, Onyejelam et al 2025), awareness and implementation of

the Act (Okoye 2011, Lawal & Ajayi 2020, Karatu et al. 2025), mainly from media studies, criminological, philosophical, sociological and psychological perspectives.

For obvious reasons, given the intimate relation between children's rights and law, legal scholars have been particularly active in children's rights scholarship (Akinwuni 2010, Toyo 2013, Olaniran 2025). Most existing studies on CRA (Nig) have investigated the legal functions of its use (Vandenhole, 2014, 2015). Other authors have approached the scholarship from the perspective of sociology of childhood and the nexus between children's rights childhood studies (Campbell, 1992; Mayall, 2000; Archad, 2015). Other approaches have connected child's rights to citizenship, gender studies, education and health (Honig, 2008, Abioye et al 2016, Opeyemi Yayi 2021).

Linguistic studies on legislations relating to children are few and the existing ones merely made references to the CRA(Nig). Language scholars are yet to start looking at the functional linguistic contents of the Act. A few linguistic studies related to children's laws include Ugot *et al* (2015) and Akpati & Oladele (2023). Ugot *et al.* highlight the role language plays the perpetration of violence against children in Cross River State, showing precisely the role of language in persuasion and coercion in order to successfully carry out the violations. Akpati & Oladele on the other hand, investigate narratives of victims of child abuse. These studies were not primarily on CRA(Nig), they only made references to the law to back up discussions on their data. The paucity of linguistic perspectives to CRA(Nig) necessitates this study. A study of the lexicogrammatical meanings in CRA(Nig) would provide objective linguistic evidence to how the lexicogrammatical elements of the English language are used to project meanings in the legal document. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap.

4. Methodology

This study is a qualitative study of the contents of CRA(Nig). It approaches the analysis of the contents by examining the lexicogrammatical choices and structuring of the linguistic elements. The analysis presents how language represents the world and inner experiences through lexicogrammatical choices, particularly the system of transitivity and selection of connectors.

Although the document consisted of 24 parts and 278 sections, the data selected consisted of 10 parts and 81 purposively selected sections of the CRA(Nig). The justification for the number of sections selected was as a result of the fact that those sections addressed the interest, rights, protection, care and supervision and custody of the Nigerian child. The parts were selected because they deal with the basic issues on child's rights and provide sufficient data comprising minimum of one clause, which is adequate for analysis of experiential meanings in the document. Also, the selected sections were adequate to be analysed, interpreted and the findings discussed so as to add to knowledge.

Theoretical Framework

The contents of the selected sections of the CRA(Nig) were closely read, focusing on the lexicogrammatical features as mirrored in the transitivity system in the clause structure. The secondary data included books, journal articles and the Internet. The analysis of the data was guided by Halliday approach to Systemic Functional Grammar. The analysis focuses on how elements like processes (verbs), participants (people, things), and circumstances (time, place) are deployed to build a representation of reality, both external events and internal thoughts or feelings.

Halliday's functional grammar recognises three kinds of social-functional 'needs'. The first is to be able to construe experience in terms of what is going on around us and inside us. The second is to interact with the social world by negotiating social roles and attitudes. The third need

is to be able to create messages with which language users can package meanings in terms of the structuring of the message. He refers to them as ideational, interpersonal and textual respectively.

The ideational metafunction is the ‘content function of language (Halliday 2007:183). It is in the ideational function that the text-producer embodies in language their experiences of the phenomena of the real world (Halliday 1973: 106). Halliday defines ideational meaning as “the representation of experience of the world that lies about us, and also inside us, the world of our imagination. It is meaning in the sense of ‘content’ (1985a: 53). The ideational function of the ‘clause’ is that of representing what in the broadest sense we can call processes: actions events, process of consciousness and relations. The ideational metafunction is sub-divided into experiential and logical metafunctions.

According to Halliday (1994:106) the experiential metafunctions represents patterns of experience. This function of language describes human experience. Here, language users describe their experience about the universe, that is, the experience of the external world. Also, reality is made up powerfully impression of experience in that it consists of ‘goings-on’, happening, doing, sensing, meaning being and becoming. All these are constructed in the grammar of the clause. According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2004:181), the system that analyses how clauses represent experience is called Transitivity. It is a system in which the verb serves as a process in which participants are depicted alongside the circumstances surrounding a communicative event. The transitivity system construes the world of experience into a manageable set of process types. These include material, mental, relational, behavioural, verbal and existential processes. The Transitivity system provides the frame of reference for interpreting language users’ experience. Halliday’s experiential meaning forms a useful theoretical framework for the analysis of the data in this research, as it discusses the clausal representation of experiences.

5. Data Analysis

The findings present the lexicogrammatical features as depicted in the choices **in** of the transitivity system showing participants roles, process types and the circumstantial roles and the frequency of occurrences. The implications of the use of the identified experiential modes are also discussed to reveal how they express meaning within the context of legal message dissemination.

Transitivity defines the range of types of process that it is possible to express through the language. Process is part of the semantic description of a clause as the clause is a mode of reflection of imposing order on the endless variation and flow of events. The transitivity system construes the world of experience into a manageable set of process types and these processes are typically expressed in the main verbs, the participant roles are expressed as subjects and complements while the circumstantial roles are expressed as prepositional phrases or adverbials signifying time, place or manner of each process type. Tables 2-4 below show at a glance a summary of the processes, participants and circumstantial roles in the data.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage of the Processes in the Data

Process Types	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Material Process</i>	335	82.5
<i>Verbal Process</i>	-	-
<i>Relational Process</i>	65	16.0
<i>Existential Process</i>	1	0.2
<i>Behavioural Process</i>	-	-
<i>Mental Process</i>	5	1.2
Total	406	

Table 2: Frequency and Percentage of the Participant Roles in the Data

Participant Roles	Frequency	Percentage
Actor	258	36
Goal	234	33
Behaver	-	-
Senser	5	0.7
Phenomenon	4	0.56
Sayer	-	-
Target	-	-
Carrier	39	5.5
Attribute	60	8.4

Identified	10	1.4
Identifier	9	1.3
Receiver	-	-
Verbiage	-	-
Extent	1	0.1
Beneficiary	92	13
Total	712	100

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage of the Circumstantial Roles in the Data

Circumstantial Roles	Frequency	Percentage
Time	49	8.5
Duration	8	1.4
Place	33	5.7
Means	17	3.0
Quality	52	9.1
Reason	19	3.3
Purpose	51	8.9
Behalf	2	0.3
Condition	195	34
Concession	8	1.4
Default	6	1.0

Comitative	59	10
Addition	3	0.5
Guise	10	1.7
Angle	32	5.6
Product	3	0.5
Matter	27	4.7
Total	574	100

The process types in the clause were mainly material and relational, as ~~can be~~ seen in Table 1 above. They account for 98.5% of the entire process types in the selected data (Material: 82.5%; Relational: 16%). This means that the processes in the clauses are mainly about ‘doing’ (Material) and ‘being’ (Relational). Material process expresses the notion that some entity ‘does’ something. Clauses in material processes refer to experiences of the external world. The participant roles involved in material process are Actor, Beneficiary and Goal. The participant roles: Actor and Goal account for 36% and 33% respectively. Most of the actors and beneficiaries in material processes in the clauses are about the child. Examples can be seen in the following clauses:

1. *No child* [ACTOR] *shall enter* [MATERIAL PROCESS] *into a contract* [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT ROLE: PRODUCT] *except as provided in this section.* [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] – Section 18(1)
2. *No person* [ACTOR] *shall remove or take* [MATERIAL PROCESS] *a child* [BENEFICIARY] *out of the custody or protection of his father or mother, guardian or*

- such other person having lawful care or charge of the child. [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: LOCATION: PLACE] against the will of the father, mother, guardian or other person [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: ACCOMPANIMENT: COMITATIVE] – Section 27(1).*
3. *No child [ACTOR] shall be employed or work [MATERIAL PROCESS] in an industrial undertaking [CIRCUMSTANTIAL: LOCATION: PLACE] and nothing in this subsection [ACTOR] shall apply [MATERIAL PROCESS] to work done by children in technical schools or similar approved institutions [BENEFICIARY] if the work is supervised by the appropriate authority [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] – Section 28(2)*
 4. *Every person, institution, service, agency, organization and body responsible for the care or protection of children [ACTOR] shall conform with [MATERIAL PROCESS] the standards established by the appropriate authorities and suitability of their staff and competent supervision. [GOAL] – Section 2(2)*

Relational process can be classified into two modes; Attribution (attributive process) and Identification (identifying process). Identifying processes are processes which determine an identity while attributive processes are to assign a quality. The participant roles involved in identifying processes are Identified and Identifier, whereas in attributive processes, they are Carrier and Attribute. In table 2 above, it can be seen that the participant roles in identifying process: Identified and Identifier account for 2.7% (Identified; 1.4% and Identifier; 1.3%) while the attributive processes with the participant roles, Carrier and Attribute account for 13.9% (Carrier: 5.5%; Attribute: 8.4%) Examples can be seen in the clauses below:

- 5 *In every action concerning a child, [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: ANGLE] whether undertaken by an individual, public or private body, institution or service, court of law or administrative or legislative authority [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] the interest of the child [IDENTIFIED] shall be [RELATIONAL PROCESS: INTENSIVE IDENTIFICATION] – Section 1*
- 6 *The persons referred to in subsection (1) of this section [IDENTIFIED] are [RELATIONAL PROCESS: INTENSIVE IDENTIFICATION]*
- (a) *the father, step-father, mother or step-mother of the child; or*
 - (b) *a person who is cohabiting with the mother or step-mother of the child, whether or not he is the putative father of the child; or*
 - (c) *the person in whose care and custody the child has been during the two years immediately preceding the date of the order or committal. [IDENTIFIER] – Section 52(2)*
- 7 *Every child [CARRIER] has [RELATIONAL PROCESS: POSSESSIVE CONTRIBUTION] a right to survival and development [ATTRIBUTE] – Section 4*
- 8 *Every child [CARRIER] has [RELATIONAL PROCESS: POSSESSIVE CONTRIBUTION] a right to freedom of thought, conscience [ATTRIBUTE] – Section 7(1)*
- 9 *Where an emergency protection order is made with respect to child who is in care [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] the care order [CARRIER] shall have [RELATIONAL PROCESS: POSSESSIVE CONTRIBUTION]*

effect [ATTRIBUTE *subject to the emergency protection order* [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CAUSE: REASON] – Section 55 (11)

10 *No parental responsibility agreement* [CARRIER] *shall have* [RELATIONAL PROCESS: POSSESSIVE ATTRIBUTION] *effect* [ATTRIBUTE] *for the purpose of this act* [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CAUSE: REASON], *unless it is made in the form and manner prescribed by regulations made by the Chief Justice of Nigeria under this section.* [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONDITION: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] – Section 68 (2)

Clear cases of intensive identification are represented in some clauses, where the child, parents or something that has to do with them is identified. There are also cases of possessive attribution where the child is seen as possessing certain rights or certain responsibilities, which are assigned to parents, guardians or other care givers of the child. CRA therefore from this experiential analysis, portrays who a child is, what rights a child possesses, what a child should benefit from the society, what persons, institutions, agencies, organisations and the entire society should ‘do’ to a child.

Mental and existential processes are the two other processes identified in the data. They account for 1.4% (1.2% and 0.2% respectively). However, there are no Verbal and Behavioural processes in the sections analysed. The mental processes have to do with perception, affection or cognition, that is, someone hearing, liking, knowing or understanding something. Here, the Phenomena are being affected, heard or perceived by the court or someone else in favour of the child. A few examples include:

- 11 *Before a forfeiture order is made under this section, [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: LOCATION: TIME], the Court [SENER] shall hear [MENTAL PROCESS: PERCEPTION] the author, copyright owner or main publisher of the harmful publication [PHENOMENON] if he so wishes [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] – Section 38(5)*
- 12 *No application for the discharge of an emergency protection order [SENER] shall be heard [MENTAL PROCESS: PERCEPTION] by the court [PHENOMENON] before the expiry of the period of seventy-two hours beginning with the making of the order [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: LOCATION: TIME] - Section43(9)*
- 13 *Nothing in the provision of subsections (1) and (2) of this section [SENER] shall affect [MENTAL PROCESS: AFFECTION] the rights of parents, and, where applicable [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: ANGLE] legal guardians to exercise reasonable supervision and control over the conduct of their children [PHENOMENON] – Section 8(3)*

The clauses 11 - 13 show that somebody *hears something or is being affected by something so that the well-being or protection of a child is guaranteed or the rights of a child are being adhered to.*

The predominant circumstantial role in the sections analysed is that of Condition. It has the highest number of occurrences. For instance, 195 of the 574 circumstantial roles in the sections are those of condition and this represents 34% of the total number of occurrences. The next Circumstantial role is Comitative with a total number of 59 occurrences representing 10% of the circumstantial roles. This is followed by Quality, Purpose and Time which represent 9.1%, 8.9% and 8.5% respectively. The least occurring circumstantial roles are circumstances of Addition, Product and Behalf with Addition and Behalf having a total number of 3 occurrences each and

Behalf with a total of 2 occurrences. Circumstances of Addition and Product represent 0.5% each while Behalf represents 0.3%.

Condition is an uncertain future act or event whose occurrence or nonoccurrence determines the existence or extent of an interest or rights or obligations or which initiates, halts or terminates the performance of a duty. The existence of conditions, cases or events stating why a particular right should be initiated or withdrawn may be the reason for its predominance among the circumstantial roles in the selected sections in the Act. For instance, section 68(5):

14 *Where the Court makes a residence order in favour of the father or the mother of the child [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] it [ACTOR] shall, if the father or mother would not otherwise have parental responsibility for the child, [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: CONTINGENCY: CONDITION] also make [MATERIAL PROCESS] an order [GOAL] under subsection (1) of this section giving the father or mother that responsibility [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: LOCATION; PLACE] Section 68 (5)*

reveals a condition in which a particularly responsibility is to be adhered to in the future by the parents of a child due to an order by the court. Circumstantial role is followed by comitative. The circumstantial role of comitative used in the analysed sections of the CRA(Nig) reveals that certain duties are given to parents, guardians, institutions or the entire society with respect to the child. For instance, in sections 44(6) and 55 (14)

15 *While a child is being kept in police protection [TIME] the designated officer [ACTOR] may apply [MATERIAL PROCESS] on behalf of an emergency protection order to be made under section 42 of this Act [PURPOSE] with respect to the child*

[CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: ACCOMPANIMENT: COMITATIVE] Section 44 (6)

16 *The provisions of the First Schedule to this Act [CARRIER] shall have [RELATIONAL POSSESSIVE CONTRIBUTION] effect [ATTRIBUTE] with respect to financial relief [COMITATIVE] for children [BENEFICIARY]*
Section 55 (14)

The circumstantial role (Comitative) used in the clauses above reveal certain duties performed by appropriate authority with respect to the child for their safety or protection. The circumstantial role of Quality reveals how something is done for or on behalf of the child so that the rights of the child is adhered to or certain obligations are carried out on their behalf. For instance, section 56(2)

17 *On an application made by the State Government, appropriate authority or the child [CIRCUMSTANTIAL ELEMENT: MATTER] the Court [ACTOR] may make [MATERIAL PROCESS] such order [GOAL] as it considers appropriate [QUALITY] with respect to the Contact which is to be allowed between the child and a named person. [COMITATIVE]* Section 56(2)

The clause above reveals how or the order in which something is done for ~~the~~ a child. The circumstantial roles of Purpose and Time follow Quality. The dominance of Circumstantial roles of Condition, Comitative, Quality, Purpose and Time show that the experience of users of the CRA(Nig) is based on these circumstantial issues which determine the existence or extent of the rights and obligations.

6. Other Lexicogrammatical Features in CRA(Nig)

Other prominent lexicogrammatical features of the CRA (Nigeria) are the abundant restrictive connectors such as *with respect to* which is found in 20 of the 80 sections that constitute the data for this study and accounts for 31.2%. *Subject to* has a total number of 15 occurrences and represents 23.4% of the connectors. *Notwithstanding* occurs in 9 places and accounts for 14% of the data while *in accordance with* has a total number of 8 occurrences with 12.5%. The least occurring connectors are *accordingly* which occurs 6 times, *in respect of*, which occurs 4 times and *pursuant to* which has a total number of 2 occurrences. These connectors have percentage of 9.4%, 6.3% and 3.1% respectively. Table 6 below summarises the use of sentence connectors in the data.

Table 4: Connectors in the Data

Connectors	Frequency	Percentage
<i>With respect to</i>	20	31.2
<i>Subject to</i>	15	23.4
<i>Notwithstanding</i>	9	14
<i>In accordance with</i>	8	12.5
<i>Accordingly</i>	6	9.4
<i>In respect of</i>	4	6.3
<i>Pursuant to</i>	2	3.1
Total	64	100

These connectors make references to key stakeholders in the context of the discourse, such as *the child*, as in *with respect to a child*; parents (*subject to parental control*); *in respect of* (*in respect of*

the father or mother of a child); in accordance with (*in accordance with rules*); pursuant to (*pursuant to sub-section (5)*), and so forth. The connectors are used to express relationships between ideas with the clause. For example:

18 *The making of a care order **with respect to** a child who is subject to a contact order, a prohibited steps order, a residence order or a specific issue order, discharges the contact order, the prohibited steps order, the residence order or the specific issue ; order. [Section 55(9)]*

19 *Every child is entitled to freedom of movement **subject to** parental control which is not harmful to the child [Section 9(1)]*

20 *Where an order is made by the Minister in pursuance of subsection (1) of this section, no person shall give or acquire the custody, possession or control of or remove a child from any part of the state specified in the order except, **in accordance with** rules made by the Minister and such rules may be in general or in respect of any particular part of a State. [Section 79(2)]*

21 *Every child has a right to a name and **accordingly** shall be given a name on his birth or on such other date as is dictated by the culture of the parents or guardian. [Section 5(1)]*

- 22 *Where subsection (5) of this section requires the Court to make an order under subsection (1) of this section **in respect of** the father or mother of a child, the Court shall not bring that order to an end at any time while the residence order concerned remains in force.*
- 23 *If the appropriate authority decides that it would review the case **pursuant to** subsection (5) of this section, it shall determine the date on which that review is to begin. [Section 59(6)]*

From the data above, the word *with respect to* for instance, is used to link the phrase *the making of care order* to the rest of the sentence in order to carry out the thought of this law thereby making meaning.

Another lexical feature dominantly used in the CRA (Nigeria) is the use of certain determiners which are unique and specific determiners of nouns in legal documents. The determiner *such* is dominant in many of the sections analysed with 52 occurrences. There is the use of *such* with some nouns in the sections analysed. *Such fine* occurs in section 15(6), *such measure* in section 16 (1), *such fine and imprisonment* in section 23, 24(2), 27(1), 28(3), 33(2), *such direction* in section 42(5), 62(1) (2) (3). The use of this unique and specific determiner is peculiar to legal documents as it is used to indicate or identify a particular item that is specifically under consideration and therefore should be given more attention by the user of the document.

Another determiner which is predominantly used in the CRA(Nig) is the determiner *every*. This determiner has 26 occurrences in the data and is used along with some nouns. *Every child* occurs in sections 4, 5(1), 6, 7(1), 8(1), 9(1), 11, 12(1) (2), 13(1), 15(1), ... *the birth of every child*

occurs in section 5(2), *every government* occurs in sections 12(3), 13(2) (3), *every parent* in sections 13(4) (5), 15(2)(3) and *every person* in section 16(2). The use of *every* with other nouns in the data shows that each *child, parent, government* or *institution* that has the care, protection or responsibility of the child is considered separately as an individual entity and the interest of each child is paramount. The word *every* is used to ensure comprehensive coverage of a rule or requirement and make an all-encompassing statement that applies to all individuals or entities being referred to.

Other dominant lexical feature used in the CRA(Nig) include *custody, damage, contract, offence and order*. *Order* as a noun occurs in 88 places in the 80 sections that constitute the data for this study. *Offence* occurs 25 times, *custody* makes a total of 14 occurrences while *contract* and *damage* have 4 and 2 occurrences respectively. Examples are below:

24 *Where a State Government has obtained an emergency protection **order** with respect to a child, it shall make, or cause to be made, such enquiries as it considers necessary to enable it to decide what action it should take to safeguard or promote the welfare of the child.* [Section 45(2)]²⁴,

25 *A person who contravenes the provisions of subsection (1) and (2) of the section commits an **offence** and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for life.* [Section 25(2)]

- 26 *No person shall remove or take a child out of the **custody** or protection of his father or mother, guardian or such other person having lawful care of charge of the child against the will of the father, mother, guardian or other person. [Section 27(1)]*
- 27 *A child may bring an action for **damages** against a person for harm or injury caused to the child willfully, recklessly, negligently or through neglect before, during or after the birth of that child. [Section 17(1)]*
- 28 *No child shall enter into a **contract** except as provided in this section. [Section 18 (1)]*

It is worthy of note that the use of these words in the data gives them some prominent focus in the clauses, spelling out the procedures for protecting a child from physical, mental or emotional harm (24); what constitute an offence against a child (25); issues about the custody of a child (26); a child's capacity to take legal actions for damages (27); and the inability of a child to enter into a contract with other individuals (28) Although the words deployed are general English expressions, in the legal context of usage, they constitute legal jargons, which clarify the processes, roles, and specific meanings in CRA(Nig).

7. Conclusion

This paper has analysed lexicogrammatical features of the Child's Rights Act (Nigeria) and showing how the Act mirrors experiential meanings in the clause structures of the messages in the data. In addition to the transitivity system that analysed the process types, participant and

circumstantial roles, other prominent lexicogrammatical features, such as specific sentence connectors and legal jargons were analysed to show how meaning is encoded and projected in the clauses. The analysis reveals that CRA(Nig) is a document that contains carefully chosen lexicogrammatical resources structured to reveal the experience of the world, which includes expected actions, events, states and consciousness in relation to how children should be handled by all stakeholders in ensuring their well-being.

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